

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Report Proline-rich Tyrosine Kinase 2 beta (PTK2 β): Protein Constructs, Cryo-EM, Biophysical Assay, and Biochemical Assay

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SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is associated with the progressive memory loss and cognitive impairment that occurs as age progresses. The amyloid beta (A β) plaque-induced neuron death in the aging brain is believed by many to be the primary cause and diagnosis of AD [1]. To date, there is a paucity in therapeutic interventions that can slow or halt the AD progression. A non-receptor proline-rich protein tyrosine kinase (PTK2b) is a calcium-dependent kinase highly enriched in forebrain neurons [2]. It is also a signaling protein involved in various pathways resulting in contrasting functions [3]. Traditionally, PTK2b has been considered an oncogene and targeted for development of anti-cancer drugs. Its diversity in function and recent bioinformatic analysis has revealed a potential role of PTK2b in the risk for late-onset AD [4]. Based on existing studies, the complex mechanisms of PTK2b are hypothesized to contribute to amyloid toxicity and tauopathy that may lead to a neuronal functional deficits in the microglia [5]. Thus, the implication that PTK2b activity contributes to the development of AD at various stages supports the hypothesis that novel therapeutics that selectively inhibit PTK2b may be developed to treat AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The gene PTK2b also known as PKB, PTK, FAK2, PYK2 CAKB, *etc.* encodes for a cytoplasmic protein tyrosine kinase. This protein is a member of the Focal-adhesion kinase (FAK) family and is involved in the calcium-induced regulation of ion channels and also implied in the activation of kinase signaling pathways [6], [7]. The expressed protein gets activated by intramolecular tyrosine phosphorylation. PTK2b is a multi-domain, non-receptor tyrosine kinase with 1009 amino acids that is expressed mainly in hematopoietic and neuronal tissues. It includes

an *N*-terminal FERM domain, followed by a catalytically active kinase domain and a C-terminal focal adhesion targeting (FAT) domain [2]. The FERM domain is involved in the regulatory function and oligomerization of kinase [8]. The Kinase domain gets activated by autophosphorylation of a tyrosine (Y402) located in the linker section between FERM and Kinase domains [9]. Other autophosphorylation sites including Y579 and Y580 also affect the regulatory mechanism. The central kinase domain has been targeted for potential inhibitory mechanisms in the past. The FAT domain which also contains an autophosphorylation site (Y881) is known for association with the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling and cancer progression pathways. Human genetic studies and the Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) for Alzheimer's disease (AD) identified PTK2B as one of the risk factors for late-onset AD (LOAD) [10]. A phenotypic examination relates the indirect suppress regulation of tau phosphorylation hence mediating the $A\beta$ -driven deficits [5]. This induces an automatic response for further and immediate study of the implied association in the context of the PTK2b as one of the targets for the development of new drug targets.

RESULTS

PROTEIN PURIFICATION

The PTK2b protein was expressed and purified from bacterial and Baculovirus-based expression systems. Two different plasmid constructs have been cloned for expression of the full-length PTK2b (FERM-Kinase-FAT domains) and the enzymatically active kinase domain alone. The two constructs that code for full-length PTK2b and the Kinase 2 domain of PTK2b were purified to a high degree (Figure 1 and Figure 2), with a yield of approximately 1.8 mg/L and 3.6 mg/L, respectively.

Figure 1: Purification of the kinase domain of *E. coli*. **(A)** The size-exclusion chromatography of kinase domain of PTK2b with active fraction indicated by orange arrow. **(B)** Western blotting with His-tag-based primary antibody to confirm the soluble expression and purification of the kinase domain of PTK2b.

Figure 2: Purification of PTK2b full-length protein from Rosetta2 (DE3) cells. Relatively pure protein was obtained after anion-exchange chromatography as the final step in the purification of full-length PTK2b.

STRUCTURAL DATA

Crystallization conditions have been established for PTK2b kinase purified from *E. coli* expression. Crystals grown in these conditions routinely diffract to better than 3Å resolution. A PTK2b(kinase) *apo* structure at ~2.9 Å has been obtained (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Structural determination of PTK2b kinase domain. (A) Crystal from the drop. (B) X-ray structure of kinase domain of PTK2b in *apo* form determined to be 3.2 Å. The conserved kinase DFG motif is highlighted in color in the X-ray structure of PTK2b kinase.

ASSAYS

KINETIC ASSAY

A real-time biochemical assay has been established for PTK2b to measure the kinase activity. The PhosphoSens kinase assay is a one-step, label-free, sensitive fluorescence-based assay to detect the tyrosine kinase activity. A synthetic sensor peptide with an 8-hydroxyquinoline derivative (sulfonamide-oxime, *Sox*) utilizes the Chelation-Enhanced Fluorescence (ChEF) upon phosphorylation upon coordination with Mg (II). The kinase substrate is highly specific to the PTK2b kinase (Figure 4). The assay is able to detect the kinase activity by the enzyme in a concentration-dependent manner. It is also able to detect the activity of the various inhibitors.

Figure 4: A real-time kinetic assay to determine the kinetic parameters for the (A) Full-length PTK2b and (B) kinase domain of PTK2b.

THERMODYNAMIC ASSAY

An Isothermal Titration Calorimetry (ITC) based determination of thermodynamic parameters such as dissociation constants (K_D), enthalpy, and entropy due to the association with the selective inhibitor molecules was performed (Figure 5 and Table 1). Also, the change in the protein inversion temperature (T_i) was measured by using a label-free, internal fluorescence-based method carried out by A system *i.e.*, Tycho from NanotemperTM. Results indicate a stronger interaction between the kinase domain and ATP-based inhibitors such as ATP γ S and AMP-PNP (Table 2).

Figure 5: ITC of PTK2b (kinase domain). (A) the interaction of non-hydrolysable ATP analog *i.e.*, ATP γ S with PTK2b kinase domain. (B-D) The interaction of PTK2b kinase domain with various potent type I inhibitors.

Table 1: The thermodynamic parameters of PTK2b kinase domain interacting with different ATP-based inhibitors.

#	[PTK2b] (μ M)	Ligand	[Ligand] (μ M)	N (sites)	KD (nM)	Δ H (kcal/mol)	Δ G (kcal/mol)	-T Δ S (kcal/mol)	Red. Chi-Sqr. (kcal/mol) ²
A	40	ATP γ S	800	0.89	11300	-6.8	-6.75	0.045	0.020
B	20	TAD0000067	200	0.66	34.9	-7.36	-10.2	-2.81	0.221
C	20	TAD0000117	200	0.63	28.8	-8.47	-10.3	-1.82	0.065
D	20	TAD0410159	200	0.68	46.2	-9.26	-10	-0.748	1.3

Table 2: The inversion temperature measured for the kinase and full-length PTK2b purified from bacterial source.

Sample	T _i (°C)	ΔT _i
PTK2b ^{kinase}	56.3	0
PTK2b ^{kinase} + AMP-PNP (2mM)	59.5	3.2
PTK2b ^{kinase} + Mg ²⁺ + AMP-PNP (2mM)	59.3	3
PTK2b ^{kinase} + ATP (1mM) + Mg ²⁺ (5mM)	56.8	0.5
PTK2b ^{kinase} + ATP _γ S (2mM) + Mg ²⁺ (5mM)	60.7	4.4
PTK2b ^{kinase}	56.5	0
P ^{FL} 18	52.9	-3.6
P ^{FL} 18 + ATP _γ S (2mM)	58.2	1.7
P ^{FL} 18 + AMP-PNP (2 mM)	55.7	-0.8

FUTURE PLANS

More than 15 follow-up compounds have been selected for further biophysical studies based on the catalytically active domain. Detailed biophysical and structural studies will be performed in order to understand the difference in the interaction mode and efficacy and selectivity of the proposed inhibitory molecule/s. Also, new sites will be traced for highly specific inhibitor-protein interaction based on the full-length structure of the PTK2b that has been elusive to date. For this, activity assays will be used to measure any modulatory effect the compounds have. Compounds will be further optimized using iterative crystallographic methods and activity assays, with a particular focus on compounds that are highly selective and active against full-length PTK2b.

CONCLUSION

The biochemical studies presented here allow the comparison of domain-related protein stability and activity differences. Such difference can be further pursued as the possibility of exploring the development of highly selective and potent inhibitor molecules. While the structural features of the kinase domain have been studied for molecular interactions, the lack of full-length structure limits the scope of variability and designing of novel drug molecules. Since the preliminary work plan has been established in order to achieve above stated goal, it will enable the identification of the new PTK2b modulators. Also, the PTK2b can upregulate the SFKs through various mechanisms and several SFK members such as Lyn also has been implicated in AD. It presents an opportunity to study the functional characterization and modulatory effect of PTK2b against other known AD targets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cloning and Expression

Expression plasmids pyk2 (FERM-Kinase-FAT and kinase domains).

Vectors:

- 1) **pFastBacHT-A-PTK2b** (Baculovirus transfer vector with *N*-terminal 6xHis-TEV tag. Ampicillin-resistance).

The plasmid is recombined with a Baculovirus genome using the *Bac-to-Bac* system (Thermo), and the DNA is transfected into SF9 cells for virus generation and propagation.

Protein sequence with the tag (Tag sequence underlined; * TEV protease cleavage site)

MSYYHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQ*GAMDPEGPAEPMVVVPVDVEKEDVRILKVCFYNS
SFNPGKNFKLVKCTVQTEIREIITSILLSGRIGPNIRLAECYGLRLKHMKSDEIHWLHPQM
TVGEVQDKYECLHVEAEWRYDLQIRYLPEDFMESLKEDRTTLLYFYQQLRNDYMQR
YASKVSEGMALQLGCLELRRFFKDMPHNALDKKSNFELLEKEVGLDLFFPKQMENLKP
KQFRKMIQQTFFQQYASLREEECVMKFFNTLAGFANIDQETYRCELIQGWNITVDLVIGP
KGIRQLTSQDAKPTCLAEFKQIRSIRCLPLEEGQAVLQLGIEGAPQALSIKTSSLAEAENM
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DETLRRPGSV DGGPQYGIAREDVVLNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGEKINVAVKTCKK
DCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHPIV KLIGIIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELGHYLERNKNSL
KVLTLVLYSLQICKAMAYLESINCVHRDIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDFGLSR YIEDEDYK
ASVTRLPIKWMSPESINFRRFTTASDVWMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFFWLENKDVIGVLEK
GDRLPKPDL CPPVLYTLMTRCWDYDPSDRPRFTEL VCSLSDVYQMEKDIAMEVDLEGG
GGSRLGAQSIQPTANLDRD TDDL VYLNVMELVRAVLELKNELCQLPPEGYVVVVKNVGL
TLRKLIGSVDDLLPSLSSRTEIEGTQKLLNKDLAELINKMRLAQQNAVTSLS EECKRQ
MLTASHTLAMDAKNLLDAVDQAKVLANLAHPPAE*

Predicted mass: 98730.60 Da

Protein sequence after tag removal:

GAMDPEGPAEPMVVVPVDVEKEDVRILKVCFYNS SFNPGKNFKLVKCTVQTEIREIITSI
LLSGRIGPNIRLAECYGLRLKHMKSDEIHWLHPQMTVGEVQDKYECLHVEAEWRYDLQ
IRYLPEDFMESLKEDRTTLLYFYQQLRNDYMQR YASKVSEGMALQLGCLELRRFFKDM
PHNALDKKSNFELLEKEVGLDLFFPKQMENLKP KQFRKMIQQTFFQQYASLREEECVM
KFFNTLAGFANIDQETYRCELIQGWNITVDLVIGPKGIRQLTSQDAKPTCLAEFKQIRSIR
CLPLEEGQAVLQLGIEGAPQALS IKTSSLAEAENMADLIDGYCRLQGEHQGSLIHPKRD
GEKRNSLPQIPMLNLEARRSHLSESCSIESDIYAEIPDETLRRPGSV DGGPQYGIAREDVV
LNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGEKINVAVKTCKKDCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHP
HIVKLIGIIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELGHYLERNKNSL KVLTLVLYSLQICKAMAYLESIN
CVHRDIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDFGLSR YIEDEDYKASVTRLPIKWMSPESINFRRFTTAS
DVWMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFFWLENKDVIGVLEKGDRLPKPDL CPPVLYTLMTRCWD
YDPSDRPRFTEL VCSLSDVYQMEKDIAMEVDLEGGGGSRLGAQSIQPTANLDRD TDDL VY
LNVMELVRAVLELKNELCQLPPEGYVVVVKNVGLTLRKLIGSVDDLLPSLSSRTEIEG
TQKLLNKDLAELINKMRLAQQNAVTSLS EECKRQMLTASHTLAMDAKNLLDAVDQAK
VLANLAHPPAE

DNA sequence (ORF)

ATGTCGTA CTACCATC ACCATC ACCATC ACGATT ACGATAT CCCAACG ACCGAAA ACCTGTA
TTTTCAGGG CGCCATGG ATCCGGA AGGTCCC GCCGAACCA ATGGTCGTGGT ACCGGTGGATG
TTGAGAAGG AGGATGTG CGTATCCT CAAGGTGTG TTTCTACT CTAACCTTTT CAACCCAGGA
AAGA ACTTTTAA ATTAGTAAA ATGCACTGT ACAGACTG AGATCAG AGAAATTAT CACCTCCAT
TCTTTTATC AGGACGCAT CGGGCCGA ATATCAGG CTAGCCG AGTGCTAC GGTCTACGGCTTA
AACACATGAA ATCGGATG AGATCCATT GGCTGCACCCT CAAATGAC CGTGGGGAA GTCCA
AGACAAGTAC GAGTGTCT GCATGTGCA AGCCGAGTGG CGGTATGACCT CCAGATACGTTACC
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CAGCTTGCCTAGTTCTTCCC GAACGGAGATAGAAGGAACGCAGAA GTTACTTAACAAAGAC
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GGAATGCAAGCGTCAGATGCTGACAGCGTCCCATACTTAGCCATGGATGCAAAGAACCTG
CTCGACGCTGTGGACCAAGCGAAAGTCCTTGCAAACCTCGCGCACCCGCCAGCAGAATAA

- 2) **pET28a_PTK2b** (Bacterial transfer vector with *N*- and *C*-terminus 6x-His and N-terminus TEV tag. Kanamycin resistance)

Protein sequence with tag (Tag sequence underlined; * TEV protease cleavage site)

MGSSHHHHHHSSGENLYFQ*GHMEGPAEPMVVVVPVDVEKEDVRILKVCFYSNSFNPGKNFKLV
KCTVQTEIREIITSILLSGRIGPNIRLAECYGLRLKHMKSDEIHWLHPQMTVGEVQDKYECLHVEA

EWRYDLQIRYLPEDFMESLKEDRTTLLYFYQQLRNDYMORYASKVSEGMALQLGCLELRRFFK
DMPHNALDKKSNFELLEKEVGLDLFFPKQMENLKPQFRKMIQQTFFQYASLREEECVMKFF
NTLAGFANIDQETYRCELIQGWNITVDLVIGPKGIRQLTSQDAKPTCLAEFKQIRSIRCLPLEEGQA
VLQLGIEGAPQALSIIKSSSLAEAEENMADLIDGYCRLQGEHQGSLIHPKDGKRNLSLPQIPMLNL
EARRSHLSESCSIESDIYAEIPDETLRRPHMVDGGPQYGIAREDVVLNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTN
HKGEKINVAVKTCKKDCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHPHIVKLIIGIIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELG
HYLERNKNSLKVLTLLVLYSLQICKAMAYLESINCVHRDIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDGFLSRYIED
EDYYKASVTRLPIKWMSPEINFRFTTASDVWMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFFWLENKDVIGVLEK
GDRLPKPDLCPPVLYTLMTRCWDYDPSDRPRFTELVCSLSDVYQMEKDIAMEVDLEGGGGSRL
GAQSIQPTANLDRDLDLVYLNVMELVRAVLELKNELCQLPPEGYVVVVKNVGLTLRKLIGSV
DLLPSLPSSSRTEIEGTQKLLNKDLAELINKMRLAQQNAVTSLSSEECKRQMLTASHTLAMDAKNL
LDAVDQAKVLANLAHPPAELEHHHHHH

Predicted mass: 99016.93 Da

Protein sequence after tag removal:

GHMEGPAEPMVVVPVDVEKEDVRILKVCFYNSNFNPGKNFKLVKCTVQTEIREIITSILLS
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LPEDFMESLKEDRTTLLYFYQQLRNDYMORYASKVSEGMALQLGCLELRRFFKDMPHN
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LEEGQAVLQLGIEGAPQALSIIKSSSLAEAEENMADLIDGYCRLQGEHQGSLIHPKDGK
RNSLPQIPMLNLEARRSHLSESCSIESDIYAEIPDETLRRPHMVDGGPQYGIAREDVVLNR
ILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGEKINVAVKTCKKDCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHPHIV
KLIIGIIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELGHYLERNKNSLKVLTLLVLYSLQICKAMAYLESINCVHR
DIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDGFLSRYIEDEDYYKASVTRLPIKWMSPEINFRFTTASDV
WMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFFWLENKDVIGVLEKGDRLPKPDLCPPVLYTLMTRCWDYD
PSDRPRFTELVCSLSDVYQMEKDIAMEVDLEGGGGSRLGAQSIQPTANLDRDLDLVYLN
VMELVRAVLELKNELCQLPPEGYVVVVKNVGLTLRKLIGSVDDLPSLPSSSRTEIEGTQ
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ANLAHPPAELEHHHHHH

DNA sequence (ORF):

ATGGGCAGCAGCCATCATCATCATCACAGCAGCGGCGAGAATCTTTATTTTCAGGGCCA
TATGGAGGGACCAGCTGAACCCATGGTTGTCGTACCAGTTGACGTCGAGAAGGAGGATGTG
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 GCAAAGGTCCTGGCTAATTTGGCGCATCCGCCGGCAGAGCTCGAGCACCACCACCACC
 ACTGA

3) pET11a-PTK2b-Kinase (Bacterial transfer vector with *N*-terminus 6x-His and TEV tag.
 Ampicillin resistance)

Protein sequence with tag (Tag sequence underlined; * TEV protease cleavage site)

MHHHHHHENLYFQ*GSMGGPQYGIAREDVVLNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGEKINVAVKTC
 KKDCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHPHIVKLIIGIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELGHYLERNKNSLKVLT
 LVLVSLQICKAMAYLESINCVHRDIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDFGLSRYIEDEDYKASVTRLPIK
 WMSPEINFRFRFTTASDVWMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFWLENKDVIGVLEKGDRLPKPDLCPPVL
 YTLMTRCWDYDPSDRPRFTELVCSLSDVYQMEKDIAME

Predicted mass: 34290.66 Da

Protein sequence after tag removal:

GSMGGPQYGIAREDVVLNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGEKINVAVKTCKKDCTLDNKEKFMSE
 AVIMKNLDHPHIVKLIIGIEEPTWIIMELYPYGELGHYLERNKNSLKVLT LVLVSLQICKAMAY
 LESINCVHRDIAVRNILVASPECVKLGDFGLSRYIEDEDYKASVTRLPIKWMSPEINFRFRFTTAS
 DVWMFAVCMWEILSFGKQPFWLENKDVIGVLEKGDRLPKPDLCPPVL YTLMTRCWDYDPSDR
 PRFTELVCSLSDVYQMEKDIAME

DNA sequence (ORF):

ATGCATCATCATCATCATCATGAAAACCTGTATTTTCAGGGCAGCATGGGCGGCCCGCAGTA
 TGGCATTGCGCGCGAAGATGTGGTGCTGAACCGCATTCTGGGCGAAGGCTTTTTTGGCGAAG

TGTATGAAGGCGTGTATACCAACCATAAAGGCGAAAAAATTAACGTGGCGGTGAAAACCTG
CAAAAAAGATTGCACCCTGGATAACAAAGAAAAATTTATGAGCGAAGCGGTGATTATGAAA
AACCTGGATCATCCGCATATTGTGAAACTGATTGGCATTATTGAAGAAGAACCGACCTGGAT
TATTATGGAAGTGTATCCGTATGGCGAACTGGGCCATTATCTGGAACGCAACAAAAACAGCC
TGAAAGTGCTGACCCTGGTGTGTATAGCCTGCAGATTTGCAAAGCGATGGCGTATCTGGAA
AGCATTAACTGCGTGCATCGCGATATTGCGGTGCGCAACATTCTGGTGGCGAGCCCCGGAATG
CGTGAAACTGGGCGATTTTGGCCTGAGCCGCTATATTGAAGATGAAGATTATTATAAAGCGA
GCGTGACCCGCCTGCCGATTAATGGATGAGCCCGGAAAGCATTAACTTTCCGCCGCTTTACC
ACCGCGAGCGATGTGTGGATGTTTGGCGGTGTGCATGTGGGAAATTCTGAGCTTTGGCAAACA
GCCGTTTTTTTTGGCTGGAAAACAAAGATGTGATTGGCGTGTCTGGAAAAAGGCGATCGCCTGC
CGAAACCGGATCTGTGCCCGCCGGTGTGTATACCCTGATGACCCGCTGCTGGGATTATGAT
CCGAGCGATCGCCCGCGCTTTACCGAACTGGTGTGCAGCCTGAGCGATGTGTATCAGATGGA
AAAAGATATTGCGATGGAATAA

Expression:

1) Baculoviral Protein Expression System: -

The P2 viral stock for PTK2b (FERM-Kinase-FAT domains) was generated by Genscript (Piscataway NJ.). Expression of PTK2b was performed in 2x 500mL in 2L Erlenmeyer flasks. A total of 2×10^6 SF9 cells/mL (Viability >97%) were used for the P2 viral infection at 27°C with supplementation of 100 µg/mL penicillin. The volume of P2 viral stock was adjusted based on the infection equal to the 0.1 multiplicity of Infection (MOI). The viral infection for protein production was carried out for 72 hours in a floor shaker set at 27°C with shaking at 120 rpm. The total cell count, viability, and morphology were monitored to verify the infection and protein expression. Cultures were pooled and transferred into 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged at 700*g for 30 min at room temperature. Cell supernatant was decanted into a bottle containing 10% house beach and Alconox™ detergent. Cell pellets were re-suspended in 120 mL buffer (Tris-Cl 25 mM, pH 8.0, NaCl 250 mM, Tween-20 0.2% v/v, TCEP 2 mM, Glycerol 5% v/v) and placed in -80°C for future protein purification. Cell lysate for protein purification was obtained by centrifugation of frozen pellets after thawing at 30,000*g for 45 min at 4°C.

2) Bacterial Protein Expression System: -

The plasmid vector that encodes for PTK2b (FERM-Kinase-FAT domain) was transformed into Rosetta™ 2 (DE3) (Genotype: F⁻ *ompT hsdS_B* (r_B⁻ m_B⁻) *gal dcm* (DE3) pRARE2 (*Cam^R*)) electrocompetent cells, BL21 derivatives for enhance the expression of eukaryotic proteins by containing rare codons used in *E. coli*. Single colony was picked and transferred into LB media containing 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 37 µg/mL Chloramphenicol at 37°C. The overnight culture was transferred into 2YT media for large-scale expression. The 1L 2YT media supplemented with 50 µg/mL kanamycin and 37 µg/mL Chloramphenicol was inoculated with overnight culture at 37°C. The over-expression of protein was induced by the addition of IPTG (500 µM) when OD_{600nm} reached 0.6-0.8. Later, the media was incubated for 20-24 hours at 18°C with the shaking of 150 rpm. Cell pellets were collected by centrifugation of the media in 1L centrifuge bottles at 6000 rpm for 30 min. Cells were washed twice with buffer containing Tris-Cl 25

mM, pH 8.0, and NaCl 250 mM. Later, cells were re-suspended in a Lysis buffer for protein purification as mentioned further in this report.

The over-expression of the kinase domain of the PTK2b was initiated with the transformation of vector-containing genes in the BL21 (DE3) electrocompetent cells. For large-scale expression, cells were inoculated in 1 L 2YT media and induced with IPTG (250 μ M final concentration) when OD reached 0.6-0.8 at 18°C for overnight. Once cells were harvested by centrifugation, Protein purification was achieved in two stages of FPLC-based purification that include Ni-NTA affinity chromatography and Size-exclusion chromatography mentioned later in this report.

PROTEIN PURIFICATION

Purifications were performed on cell pellets with 1 or 6 liters of expression volume. Pellets were resuspended in lysis buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% v/v glycerol, 2 mM TCEP, 0.2% v/v Tween-20, 50 μ g/mL Lysozyme) to a volume of 20 ml per gram expressed cells. The cells were lysed using sonication on ice with 5 seconds on, and 15 seconds off for 15 minutes. Lysate was cleared by centrifugation at 50,000*g for 45 minutes at 4°C.

Active protein was purified in three consecutive chromatographic steps. At first, the clear lysate was loaded onto the HisTrap HP column (CV: 5mL). The column was washed with 10 CV wash buffer (25 mM Tris-CL pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP) and the protein was eluted using gradient elution (10 CV) of elution buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 250 mM NaCl, 1000 mM imidazole, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). The active fractions were pooled and concentrated to a volume of 1-2 mL by using MilliporeSigma™ Amicon™ Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter (10 MWCO). The concentrated fractions were further injected into a Superdex 200 16/60 column in gel filtration buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 25 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). Active fractions were combined. In the final step of purification, pooled fractions were loaded onto an anion-exchange column (MonoQ 10/100 GL) equilibrated with low-salt buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 20 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP) and protein was eluted with high salt buffer (25 mM Tris-Cl pH 8.0, 1000 mM NaCl, 0.2% Tween-20, and 2 mM TCEP). Active fractions were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and quantified by using the Bradford method.

Crystallization, Data collection, and processing

Crystallization conditions were screened at 4 and 20°C by sitting drop vapor diffusion using 100 nl drops with ratios of 2:1, 1:1, and 1:2. Screens were set up around identified conditions. *Apo* PTK2b kinase crystals were grown from protein at 18 mg/ml in 0.1M bis-tris Propane: HCl, pH 7.0, 35% Microlytic mix. The crystals were cryoprotected by the addition of a 9 μ l reservoir to the drop added to 1 μ l 100% PEG400.

For the *apo* structure, data were collected at Diamond Light Source on beamline I03 to a resolution of 1.48 Å. Data processing: The data were integrated with Dials and scaled with Aimless. The structure was determined by molecular replacement with Phaser using PDB id 3ET7 as a model. The structures were refined using Refmac to final Rwork /Rfree.

PhosphoSens Kinase Assay

The assay was performed in a Corning, low-volume 384-well, black flat-bottom polystyrene NBS microplates (3824) at 30°C. The enzyme assay reaction contains the kinase reaction buffer (50 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 0.1% Brij-35, 100 mM MgCl₂), ATP 1 mM, DTT 1 mM, EGTA 0.55 mM, Kinase substrate 10 μM and enzyme in various concentration (range 2 nM – 15 μM). The reaction was initiated by adding enzyme into the reaction mixture and the enzyme was diluted in dilution buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 0.01% v/v Brij-35, 5% v/v Glycerol, 1 mg/mL Bovine Serum Albumin). The reaction was monitored by fluorescence measurements with λ_{ex} at 360nm and λ_{em} at 492nm recorded in kinetic mode (readings every 30 seconds for 30-180 minutes). Inhibitor compounds were added to the reaction mixture to record and analysis of the inhibitory effects of the molecules.

Isothermal Titration Calorimetry and Inversion Temperature Determination

The experiments were carried out at 298 K with 19 injections of small molecules in the syringe and protein in the bulk *i.e.*, in the cell. The appropriate experimental controls were performed too. 270 μl protein (20 μM) was titrated against 40μl molecules (200 μM) with a 1:10 protein: ligand ratio. For Tycho, 100 nM final protein concentration was loaded into capillaries for inversion temperature determination.

PTK2b	1	MSGI-----EPLSRVK--GGT--LRRVEGPAAEPMVVVDFDVEKEDVRLIKVCFYNSFNH-----GKPFQ--PACTVVT	65
PTK2 (FAK)	1	MAAAVLDENLNHTSISSTKTELOTGMRITPGAME-----RVIKVFHYFESNGEPTWASITIRGQDATDVRG	66
PTK2b	66	ETKRTTSTGSSGSESSNTRLAEVYQDRLEHNSDETHWHPMTVGEVQKRYGDLHVEALWRYDLDTRYLPEDENESLR	145
PTK2 (FAK)	67	LIQNVDSH-----KVIHVAICYFRLSHLSRSEVWVHVMGVSSVREKYTLAHVPELWXYTLRTRYLPEDEINQPT	138
PTK2b	146	EDPTTLLTFYQQLDNDYMCRYASKVSEGMALQIGLEDRRTKMPFNALDKKNFELLEKVVGLDFFPKQMQENLRK	225
PTK2 (FAK)	139	EDGHTLNFYQOVKSDYMEITADQVDQETALKIGCLELRRITWMMGNALDKKNYEVLKIVGLKRFEPKILLOSVKR	218
PTK2b	226	QIRRMVQPTFQYASLREEECVMKFFNTLAGPANIQCETTCRHLIQWNIVDVIIEP--ITRQTSQDAKPTCLAEFQ	304
PTK2 (FAK)	219	TLRRVQOTEQFAHLNBERSTIKFEETLSPVYRDECTKCALGSEWIVVELATPEEGLSKITOKGCPTSLADEG	298
PTK2b	305	TRITPCPLREG--DAVTLQLECAEQALSITSSLAEAENMDLIDCYCRVQGEHQGSIITRPKDCGKRNLEPTEPIH	382
PTK2 (FAK)	299	VQVQYVNSDKESSVMDQLVAGVEEPLTVRPSLSTIAENMDLIDCYCRVNGTQSGSIITRPKEGEL--SLPTEGL	376
PTK2b	383	NLEARRHLSKSCITESDIYAEIDETLRREGGPOYGIAREDVVLNRILGEGFFGEVYEGVYTNHKGKINVAVKTC	459
PTK2 (FAK)	377	ANAEKQMTNRAVAVSETDDYAEIDEEETVYMESTRDVEIQERIELGRICIGEGQFGDVHQGIYMSPENPALAVAIKTC	456
PTK2b	460	KKDCTLDNKEKFMSEAVIMKNLDHPHIVKLVIGITEEEPWIIIMELYFYGELGHYLERNKNSLKVLTLVLYSLQICKAMAY	539
PTK2 (FAK)	457	KNCTSDSVREKFLQEALTMRFQDHPHIVKLVIGITENPVWIIIMELCTLGELRSFLQVRKYSLDLASLILYAYQLSTALAY	536
PTK2b	540	LESINCVHRDIAVRNIVASPECVRLGDFGLSRYIEDEDYRKASVTRLPIKMMSPESINFRFRFTASDVWVFVCMWEIL	619
PTK2 (FAK)	537	LESKRFFVHRDIAARNVLVSSNDCVRLGDFGLSRYMEDSTYYKASKGKLPKMMAPESINFRFRFTSASDVWVFVCMWEIL	616
PTK2b	620	SFGKQPFWLENKDVIGVLEKGRLEKFDLCPFVLTLMTRCWDYDESDRPRFTELVCSLSDVY-----QMEKDIAEQE	694
PTK2 (FAK)	617	MHGKVPFQGVKNNQVIGRIENGERLMPFPNCPPTLYSLMFKCWAYDPSRRPRFTELKAQLSTILEEKAQQEERMRESR	696
PTK2b	695	RNARYRTPKILEPTAFQEPKPKPSRPKYRPPQTNLLAPKQ-----FQVPEGLCASSPTLTSPEMYPSVNLSTHTPP	767
PTK2 (FAK)	697	RQATVSW---DSGGSDEAPPKPSRPGYPSRPSSEGFYPSQHMVQTNHYQVSGYPGSHGI TAMAGSIYPGQASLLDQTD	772
PTK2b	768	L--HRHNVFKRHSMSREEDFIQFSSREEAQQLWEAEKVKMRQILDKQQKQMVEDYQWLRQEEKSLDPMVYMNDKS-----	839
PTK2 (FAK)	773	SWNHRPQEIAMWQPNVEDSTVLDLRLGIGQVL---PTHLMEERLIRQQQEMEEDQRWLEKERERFLKPDVRLSRGSDIDREDG	849
PTK2b	840	---PLTPE---KEVGYLEFTGPPQKPPALGAQ-----SIQPTANLERTDDELVLAVM	885
PTK2 (FAK)	850	SLQGPIGNQHIYQPVGKDPAAAPPKPPFPGAPGHGLGSLASLSSPADSYNEGVLQPOET SPPPTANLDRSNDKVENVT	929
PTK2b	886	ELVRAVLELKNELQQLPPEGVVVVKNVGLTLKRLIGSVDDLPSLSSSRTEIEGTQKLLNKDLAELINQRLAQONAV	965
PTK2 (FAK)	930	GLVKAVIEMSSKIQPAPEEYVPMVKEVGLALSTLLATVDETIPLLASTHREIEMAQKLLNSDLGELINQKLAQQYVM	1009
PTK2b	966	PSLSEECRQMLTASHTLAVDAKNLLDAVDQAKVLANLAHPAE	1009
PTK2 (FAK)	1010	TSLQQEYKQMLTAAHALAVDAKNLLSDVDQARLKMVGQTRFH-	1052

█ : FERM;

█ : Kinase;

█ : FAT

Figure 6: The domain architecture and sequential difference of PTK2b from the other member of the family *i.e.*, FAK.

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